

The Impact of Technological Revolution on the Madhwa Community

¹Nidhi Katti and ²Dr. Ramesh Kamble

¹Research Scholar, Department of Studies and Research in History, Rani Channamma University, Belagavi, Karnataka, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Studies and Research in History, Rani Channamma University, Belagavi, Karnataka, India

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18640094>

Corresponding Author: Nidhi Katti

Abstract

The Madhwa community is basically a Brahminical religious community of Deccan India. Shri Madhwacharya is founder of this community. The community is based on its traditions, customs, and math system. The technological revolution in India during the 19th 20th and 21st centuries has evolved all the existing elements of Indian society. The impact of technological revolution was so deep and fast that it entirely changed many elements in many communities. Subsequently, the technological revolution has impacted the Madhwa community. This research paper aims to evaluate the positive and negative impact of the technological revolution on the Madhwa community. The study will try to understand how the Madhwa got adjusted and mobilised itself according to the technological process. The whole of the Madhwa community is under the premises of the research scope.

The beneficiary factors of technological revolution in the promotion of the Madhwa philosophy are part of the study. The has an objective to understand how the Madhwa priests are using new technology in their priesthood profession. The study will try to construct a hypothesis on how technological revolution will impact the Madhwa community in future. Both primary and secondary sources will be used to construct this paper.

The structure of the paper will be formatted in multiple ways. Comparative method, cause and affect method, hypothesis methods are imbibed in this research. Qualitative research design, descriptive research design, fundamental research design is used in the formation process. This paper will try to explain the roots of technological revolution and how it has drastically changed many things the Madhwa community.

Keywords: Community, Technology, Revolution, Saints, Maths

Introduction

The Madhwa community is a Vaishnav Brahminical sect of Deccan India. Shri Madhwacharya is the pioneer of this community. The Madhwa community is fully based on Shri Madhwacharya's philosophy. The Madhwa community got its origin during the 12th century. The Madhwa community has a huge capacity for imbibing mobilization and adjusting through the change in centuries, new inventions, different political and administrative powers, linguistic changes, economic challenges etc. One of the major changes that occurred in the Madhwa community in the 21st century was the technological revolution. Subsequently directly and indirectly the tech revolution impacted a lot on the Madhwa community.

Objective

The study aims to evaluate the impact of the technological

revolution on the Madhwa community. The analysis of the mobilization and adaptation process of new technology imbibed by the Madhwa community in its traditions, customs, culture, economic empowerment, day-to-day life, and rituals is the prominent objective of the study. This research will describe the positive usage methods of technology cultivated by the Madhwa community in the promotion of the Madhwa philosophy, tangible, intangible culture, and heritage of their own. The critical evaluation of the impact of the technological revolution on the Madhwa community is part of the research. It also consists of a futuristic approach to the technological subjugation of the Madhwa community post 100 years.

Methodology

The study has been constructed according to qualitative, quantitative, ex-post facto, descriptive, fundamental, cause

and effect research designs. The observation method, evaluation method, constructive criticism method, hypothesis method and analysis methods have been imbibed in this research. Both primary and secondary sources have been used in the formation of this research paper.

Hypothesis

Technological Revolution has created a huge transition in the Madhwa community from its original form of the 13th century. The technological revolution in India has impacted Madhwa saints, sages, Maths, Temples, and the whole population of this community. Most of the change is positive in its form, but it has some minor negative impacts too. Unity in the Madhwa community is more powerful presently compared to the past because of technology. Through many WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter etc. groups the population relates to each other. The geographical distance of the Madhwa population has vanished through the technological revolution. The Madhwa Maths have understood the exact need of the Madhwa population through technology and are creating a prosperous environment according to it. Compared to other communities the Madhwa community has tremendously and fruitfully used technology for the benefit of their Religion, Philosophy, Maths, Temples, and population. The technological revolution has saved the Madhwa community from oblivion. Subsequently, it has helped to increase the respect towards the Madhwa traditions, customs, rituals, and philosophy in the Madhwa community.

Impact of Technological Revolution on the Madhwa Community

The 21st century is being run through technology. Each element of society is under the premise of technology. The technological revolution has also impacted religion, sub-religions, philosophies, and different communities both positively and negatively. Subsequently, the Madhwa community is one among them. Religiously, socially, politically, educationally, and economically the Madhwa community has been impacted tremendously by the technological revolution. The mobilising quality of the community helped it imbibe technology with ease. But the community has not let go of the originality, in its traditions, customs, culture and rituals; rather through the cooperation of technology, it is enhancing the value of their traditions, rituals, culture, philosophy and customs. To understand the impact more deeply below points have been made; just to give a clear vision of the positive impact of technology on the Madhwa community.

1. Helps to Promote the Madhwa Philosophy
2. Improvement in the reachability of Saints and Sages of the Madhwa Community with the Madhwa population
3. Ease in knowledge and information transfer about the day-to-day customs, and rituals of the Madhwa Community
4. Availability of Virtual Visions of Different Pious Madhwa holy, religious places
5. E-Booking facilities for Darshan at different pious religious Madhwa places
6. Participation of Madhwa Community in technology-based jobs
7. Economic Improvement of the Madhwa Community

8. Freedom for Madhwa Women through Technology
9. E-Path Shala for Religious Education
10. Modernization of the Madhwa community's rituals
11. Development of faith towards the Madhwa community and philosophy
12. Awareness about the Madhwa philosophy and culture through social media among youths of the Madhwa community
13. Unity of the Madhwa community through Social Media Platforms
14. Matrimonial Benefits

Discussion

The technological revolution has become a blessing for the promotion of the Madhwa philosophy all over the world. The Pravachans of the Madhwa Saints, Sages, and Acharyas, are being streamed live and in a recorded version on different social media platforms. These videos are shared by the Madhwa population in their social media statuses, posts, and groups through which the promotion process has taken up speed. Through short mythological, and religious stories, doodling, painting, and singing about matters related to the Madhwa community a certain number of the Madhwa population is trying to establish an insight into the Madhwa philosophy. The majority of the Madhwars who are involved in these activities are youngsters, who are using their social media accounts for the promotion of their Madhwa religion. Instagram is the main platform for such promotion activities, particularly by youths. Facebook and WhatsApp groups mainly are created by middle and old (30 to 70) aged people of the Madhwa community. In some cases, the disciples, or Acharya of Madhwa matha also create such groups which are official groups of those Madhwa maths. Each Madhwa Matha contains its own YouTube Channel, Facebook page and Instagram account through which they are promoting the philosophy, its essence, reasons to follow the philosophy, uniqueness of their own Matha etc. This step of Madhwa maths and saints has grabbed the attention of Madhwa youths a lot in the time of modernization when all the youths are attracted towards western culture. The technological revolution has helped the Saints and Sages of the Madhwa community to unite all the Madhwa youths under one group. The Facebook groups of the Madhwa community contain a population of the community in the form of members who are settled in different parts of the world. Compared to the past nine centuries presently the Madhwa maths have involved more in the promotion process.

The tangible and intangible heritage and culture of the Madhwa Maths and Madhwa Brahmin houses are being promoted through social media platforms. The importance of Brindavans, Nevidya, Upanayana, Bhaktimaarga, worshipping Hari, reasons behind the festivals, certain customs and rituals, clothing system, the Mantras, the Shlokas of the Madhwa community are presented in different platforms. This step has created awareness about the existence of many Brindavans of the Madhwa Saints and Sages and is solving the queries of youths through which strong faith in the Madhwa religion has been created in the minds of the youths.

The soul of the Madhwa community is its 'Guru Parampare' of different Madhwa Mathas. The technological revolution

has helped to promote the Guru Parampara system of the Madhwa philosophy all around the world. The 'Pravachan' (speech) of different Peethadhipatis of different Madhwa mathas is being streamed on YouTube, Instagram, and Facebook. Compared to the 19th or 20th-century promotion process and the number of listeners to the speeches done by the Madhwa scholars has increased tremendously. Madhwa Saints and Sages are teaching the daily rituals and customs to be done by a Madhwa in their day-to-day life through these social media platforms. The information concerned with any festival, the procedures to be done and not to be done during these festivals is being informed to the population of the community through social media by these Saints and Sages (Swamigalu). There are social media pages where the daily pooja of each Madhwa Matha's Swamigalu will be telecasted.

The Mathadipatis, and Swamigalu of the Madhwa Matha are using smartphones now. They are giving interviews to different news channels on religion, nation, community, heritage and culture topics through laptops and smartphones. The technological revolution has directly added some extra roles and responsibilities for the Madhwa Saints and Sages. Such as establishing political, and economic stability in the Madhwa community, enhancing spirituality, and peace, participation in socio-religious and political movements and events, and maintenance of good relationships with state and nation heads as well with different administrative ministers. Now they are more aware of the people of the Madhwa community and their needs. A big issue for the population of the Madhwa community was knowing about the daily Pachanga, day today pooja system, and items to be eaten and not to be eaten. Subsequently, through social media platforms and websites, E-Panchanga and the necessary information is being provided by the Madhwa Maths. The Madhwa women have got more freedom and liberty through the technological revolution. Technology established awareness about gender discrimination concepts in the population. Many middle-aged Madhwa women are entrepreneurs. 75% of Qualified and unqualified Madhwa women are economically independent with the help of technology. Qualified women are directly using technology in their day-to-day different domains and indirectly the unqualified Madhwa women have cultivated technology in their small-scale businesses. 70% of the total Madhwa population is working in IT sectors inside and outside India which has increased the economy of the Madhwa community.

The Madhwa community has created E-Pathshalas to teach, promote and spread awareness about Bhagwat and Haridasa literature. All over the world, there are many exam centres of Madhwa mathas that conduct the exam. The technological revolution has provided E - Dharsha opportunity for the Madhwa Brahmins of their pious religious temples and Brindavan. The daily virtual visions of different pious religious sites of the Madhwa community are a blessing to the community through which the day will be filled with happiness and satisfaction, which will directly create productivity in the work or studies of an individual who deeply believes in the Madhwa culture. Examples: - Mantralaya, Sonde, Yalaguru etc.

The Madhwa community has economically evolved a lot due to the technological revolution. As technology

developed the Madhwas mobilized themselves with it and adapted modernity for individual development, family welfare, community promotion etc. The population started getting educated and involved in different jobs. To understand the value of modern education, to select good colleges, to get knowledge and score in exams the Madhwas took the support of technology.

Role of Technology in stabilising the Madhwa Community during Covid – 19 Pandemic

The technology helped the Madhwa population a lot to cope with Covid – 19 pandemics in many forms. Examples: - Religious purposes, establishing peace in the population during the hilarious scary situation of Covid – 19 etc. The technology helped the Madhwa population to utilise the free time of two years for learning the importance of the Madhwa culture and taught the rituals, pooja rituals, Sandhyavandana Padhatti for the Madhwa population who earlier were not able to imbibe them all because of their hectic professional life. The saints and sages of the Madhwa community were continually involved in uploading videos of their Pravachan for establishing peace. Many Acharyas did online guidance for Madhwas to do the pooja, Homaa and Havans at home. The social media groups daily used to post shlokas related to the health God Dhanavantri, health, Avigna Nivarna shlokas which strengthened the Madhwa population spiritually, and mentally and created a kind of positive attitude to fight back against the virus. The Madhwas affected by Covid got willpower through listening to the Pravachans of saints and sages. The knowledge that the population of the Madhwa community got about the Madhwa philosophy, culture, and rituals influenced the population productively. Subsequently, many Madhwa's continued their religious activities in post-Covid – 19 eras too. Through technology, the Madhwa's have got matrimonial benefits to a larger extent. The Madhwa matrimonial websites connect grooms and brides of the Madhwa community who are settled all around the world. Most of the Madhwa brahmins are getting married through matrimonial websites; where they can choose their life partners according to their professions, interests, likings etc. Subsequently, the families can get grooms and brides from specific the Madhwa mathas that they are desired. The matrimonial benefits of the technological revolution have directly and indirectly become a cause for the construction of a new generation of the Madhwa community.

Critical Evaluation

The technological revolution has changed the original form of the Madhwa traditions, culture, and rituals to some extent. Technological gadgets are now part of "Madi". The saints and sages of the Madhwa community earlier were not used to travel to any other country as it was considered impurity [Ashuddha]. Subsequently whoever visited other countries belonging to particularly Madhwa community were prohibited from the community. But after the technological revolution, the Mathadipatis of Madhwa Mathas are freely travelling on flights to promote the Madhwa philosophy in other countries. The liberalization of the rituals surely is helping to make more people in the community follow them but directly and slowly is transforming the originality. Leftist, feminist, and Marxist,

concepts are making young minds of the Madhwa community hate their tradition and culture. The technological revolution has grabbed 83% of the Madhwa youths into IT industries and medical practice. Subsequently, those 83% population is situated in metropolitan cities which have made the Madhwa youths get addicted to many unworthy habits. The technological revolution has polluted the minds of some saintly Madhwa Brahmins through materialistic content. Some Madhwa women are addicted to smartphones and are not focusing on the culture of their community.

The Madhwa Community Post 100 Years under the Influence of Technology

The Madhwa community may imbibe many new technological inventions in its rituals, day-to-day life, Maths, temples, and culture but it will never lose its originality rather the technology will increase the importance and promotion process of the Madhwa community post 100 years. There will be much more modernization in providing ritualistic services. There may be the use of robots' subjugation to Homa, Havan, Yagna offerings. The future may see the concept of e-marriage, e-Homa, Havans, Yagnas etc. Decolonizing concepts of the present-day may become the cause for the construction maximum number of Madhwa Sanskrit Pathashaals all over the world.

Conclusion

The research paper "The Impact of Technological Revolution on The Madhwa Community" is an attempt made to evaluate the change that occurred during the 21st century in the premises of the Madhwa community. The paper will be concluded with the thought that Technological Revolution in India is a blessing in disguise for the Madhwa community. Technology has surely improved the economic, social, political, and educational situation of the Madhwa community. The paper will be concluded with the thought that Technological Revolution in India is a blessing in disguise for the Madhwa community.

References

1. Sharma BNK. *History of the Dvaita School of Vedānta and Its Literature*. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publishers Private Limited; c2000.
2. Hebbar BN. *The Shri Krishna Temple at Udupi: The Historical and Spiritual Centre of the Madhwa Sect of Hinduism*. New Delhi: Bharatiya Grantha Niketan; c2005.
3. Rao V. *Living Traditions in Contemporary Contexts: The Madhwa Mathas of Udupi*. New Delhi: Orient Longman Private Limited; c2002.
4. Raghavendran T. *Leading Lights of Madhwa Siddhantha: A Brief Biography of Madhwa Saints*. Coimbatore: Padmavathy Publishers; c2019.
5. Judijanto L, Siminto S, Rahman R. *The Influence of Religious Beliefs and Religious Practices on Social Cohesion in Modern Society in Indonesia*. The Eastasouth Journal of Social Science and Humanities. 2024;1(03):276. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382069925>
6. Murumba J. *Societal Implications of IT in Religion for*

Developing Countries. Science Journal of Education. 2017;5(4):144. Available from:

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320424340>

7. Sreemani P, Chandrika J. Development of Society under the Modern Technology - A Review. Ignited Minds Journals; c2013. [cited 2026 Feb 14]. Available from: <http://ignited.in/a/57943>

Creative Commons (CC) License

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license. This license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.